

TECHNICAL SCIENCES

THE POTENTIAL OF BLOCKCHAIN TECHNOLOGY IN EDUCATION: RELIABILITY, EFFICIENCY AND FUTURE STRATEGIES

Ayisha Ahmadova

Nakhchivan State University

Azerbaijan Republic, Nakhchivan AR,

Republic of Azerbaijan, Nakhchivan city, University campus, AZ7012

Abstract

In the current period, the rapid advancement of digital technologies is leading to radical changes in the education sector. One of these shifts in education is the adoption of blockchain technology. Blockchain is a technology that allows digital information to be stored in a secure and immutable form. The use of blockchain in education has a wide potential and offers significant advantages, especially in areas such as verification of diplomas and certificates and management of student records. This technology offers a variety of benefits in key areas such as data security, accuracy, transparency and efficiency.

Keywords: blockchain technology, technology, education, data security, information

Entrance

The rapid evolution of digital technologies in recent years has led to radical changes in the field of education. One of these changes is the use of blockchain technology in the education sector. Blockchain allows digital information to be stored securely and unalterably and offers significant benefits, especially in areas such as the verification of diplomas and certificates and the management of student records. This technology has the potential to revolutionize the education industry by increasing data security, accuracy, transparency and efficiency.[1]

Blockchain technology overcomes the spread of fake documents and trust issues with its decentralized and immutable data recording system. Secure management of student records and grades, and the ability for students to control their own data, facilitate collaboration and data sharing between educational institutions. Additionally, it protects student privacy and increases data security, promoting academic integrity.[8]

Blockchain also has the potential to reduce costs and increase operational efficiency in education. Verifying student records and diplomas using traditional methods is often expensive and time-consuming, but blockchain makes these processes faster, more cost-effective and more secure. In this article, the benefits and application areas of blockchain technology in education will be examined and recommendations and strategies for educational institutions will be presented. The adoption of blockchain will be an important step in shaping future education models.[7]

The Role of Blockchain Technology in Education: Data Security and Authentication

Among the opportunities offered by blockchain technology in education is the ability of students to control their own data. Thanks to blockchain-based systems, students can have a greater say in managing and sharing their educational information and certificates [1]. This allows students to gain greater awareness of themselves and manage their educational processes more consciously [2]. By using blockchain technology,

educational institutions can evaluate student achievements and performances more fairly [1]. For example, when students' achievements are stored on the blockchain, grade changes or manipulations are prevented, ensuring a fair evaluation process. At the same time, this technology can also reduce the workload of teachers and academic staff [7]. By tracking students' achievements and progress on the blockchain, teachers can manage their evaluation processes more efficiently [6].

Storing students' personal and academic information in an encrypted manner significantly reduces the risks of data breaches [1]. Additionally, ensuring students' data is only accessed by authorized individuals increases data security. This enables educational institutions to better fulfill their legal and ethical responsibilities [7]. The use of blockchain technology in education can also contribute to the prevention of academic fraud. For example, the immutability and traceability of data stored on the blockchain prevents the use of fake diplomas and certificates. This gives educational institutions and employers access to reliable information. It also promotes students' academic honesty [6].

Another important advantage offered by blockchain technology in education is also evident in lifelong learning and continuing education processes [2]. By using blockchain-based digital wallets, students can safely store all the certificates and educational documents they have obtained throughout their careers. This provides great convenience for individuals to develop their careers and acquire new skills. At the same time, employers can more reliably evaluate candidates' continuing education backgrounds. By using blockchain technology, educational institutions can develop more innovative applications in their educational processes [5]. For example, assignments and projects given to students can be stored on the blockchain to verify authenticity and timestamp. This promotes academic integrity and enables students to prove the originality of their own work [6].

Additionally, blockchain-based education platforms can offer customized educational programs

based on students' individual learning needs. This provides students with a more effective and personalized learning experience. Students can access educational materials according to their own learning pace and interests. Blockchain technology can also play an important role in reducing costs in education. Traditionally, the processes of verifying student records and diplomas are often both costly and time-consuming. However, blockchain-based systems perform these processes more economically and quickly.

By adopting blockchain technology, educational institutions can make their operations more efficient. This makes it possible for institutions to serve more students using fewer resources. Additionally, this technology allows educational institutions to develop more innovative and efficient education models, increasing their competitiveness. These benefits not only improve the quality of education but also enhance the student experience. Students can achieve their academic and career goals more easily while learning in a safer and more transparent educational environment. By integrating blockchain technology, educational institutions can provide higher levels of service to students and improve educational standards.

Blockchain technology is leading the beginning of radical changes in the field of education. By accepting this technology, educational institutions can turn to safer, more efficient and innovative education models. Blockchain provides great advantages in education in important areas such as data security, accuracy, transparency and efficiency. Adopting blockchain technology in education will be an important step for future education models. Educational institutions and students can experience a higher quality and more reliable educational experience by taking advantage of the opportunities offered by this technology. Therefore, wider adoption of blockchain technology in the education sector could usher in a revolutionary change in education. Evaluating the potential of blockchain technology in education will be a vital step for both today's and future education models. These opportunities offered by blockchain technology in education not only increase the quality and security of education, but also improve the student experience. By integrating blockchain technology, educational institutions can better serve students and raise educational standards. Therefore, wider adoption of blockchain technology in the education sector could create a revolutionary transformation in education.[6]

Conclusion

Blockchain technology has great potential in the education sector and can play an important role in the

future. This technology provides a safe, efficient and transparent environment in processes such as student registration, grade management and diploma verification. With its ability to ensure data security and accuracy, Blockchain prevents fake diplomas and documents, speeds up verification processes and reduces costs.[4]

Educational institutions should develop strategies to use blockchain technology effectively. This can start with reviewing existing processes and identifying potential areas of application. Additionally, providing the necessary infrastructure and resources will support the successful integration of technology. By explaining the importance and benefits of blockchain technology to students, trust in the technology should be increased and its acceptance encouraged.

Overall, blockchain technology can trigger a significant transformation in education, creating a trustworthy, transparent and efficient environment. By adopting this technology, educational institutions can offer students a better learning experience and be pioneers in shaping the education models of the future.

References

1. Swan, M. (2015). *Blockchain: Blueprint for a New Economy*. O'Reilly Media, Inc.
2. Tapscott, D., & Tapscott, A. (2016). *Blockchain revolution: how the technology behind bitcoin is changing money, business, and the world*. Penguin.
3. Antonopoulos, A. M. (2014). *Mastering Bitcoin: Unlocking Digital Cryptocurrencies*. O'Reilly Media, Inc.
4. Nakamoto, S. (2008). *Bitcoin: A Peer-to-Peer Electronic Cash System*. Retrieved from <https://bitcoin.org/bitcoin.pdf>
5. E. Önder, *Yönetim Bilişim Sistemleri Kapsamında Web Tabanlı İlişkisel Veritabanı Yönetim Sistemleri ve Bir Uygulama*, Yüksek Lisans Tezi, İstanbul Üniversitesi, Sosyal Bilimler Enstitüsü, 2005.
6. H. Watanabe, S. Fujimura, A. Nakadaira, Y. Miyazaki, A. Akutsu, J. J. Kishigami, "Blockchain contract: A complete consensus using blockchain", 2015 IEEE 4th Global Conference on Consumer Electronics (GCCE), 577–578, 2015.
7. Vural, Ş. Sağıroğlu, "Veritabanı Yönetim Sistemleri Güvenliği: Tehditler ve Korunma Yöntemleri", *Politeknik Dergisi*, 13(2), 71-81, 2010.
8. G. Greenspan. *Blockchains vs centralized databases*, <https://www.multi-chain.com/blog/2016/03/blockchains-vs-centralized-databases/>, 03.12.2019.